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The global environmental footprint of Switzerland's net-zero energy system uncovers impacts abroad

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National energy system models play a crucial role in climate policy. However, they often overlook environmental impacts beyond territorial greenhouse gas emissions. Here we evaluate a territorial net-zero carbon dioxide emissions energy scenario for Switzerland coupled with life cycle assessment to quantify non-domestic environmental burdens. We highlight the limitations of considering only territorial emissions. Indeed, even if domestic greenhouse gas emissions are reduced to net zero by 2050, 2 to 5 megatonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent per year persist abroad due to imports and energy-related infrastructure. These extra-territorial emissions are influenced by global climate policies. Additionally, broadening the scope of environmental indicators is crucial as more countries pursue net-zero goals. Our findings highlight trade-offs, showing how environmental impacts other than those on climate change (ecosystem impacts, air pollution, natural resource use) could increase and shift beyond Switzerland as the country electrifies its economy.

The global energy landscape is undergoing a transformative shift from fossil fuels towards a future characterized by renewable and low-carbon energy technologies¹. Central to understanding and guiding this transition are energy system models (ESMs), which are extensively used to analyze long-term transformation pathways of the energy system toward future states achieving specific energy and climate targets²⁻⁴. ESMs have influenced climate and energy policy since the 1970s. Today, ESMs are vital in understanding how to reach climate goals and shaping associated policies^{5,6}.

Switzerland exemplifies the challenges and opportunities of applying ESMs to national energy transitions. Driven by ambitious decarbonization targets and a planned nuclear phase-out, the country aims to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to net zero by 2050⁷. In this context, a prime example of ESM used for modeling domestic policy strategies is the Swiss TIMES energy model (STEM)⁸. While ESMs like STEM excel in analyzing technological and economic aspects, they fall short in assessing broader environmental impacts beyond territorial GHG emissions, such as those affecting human health and ecosystems⁹.

Reducing domestic GHG emissions may still result in GHG emissions and other environmental impacts associated with infrastructure and industrial activities beyond national borders¹⁰. To address this issue, cost-optimal ESM-based transition scenarios should consider life-cycle environmental externalities to detect spatial burden shifts associated with

domestic production and consumption¹¹. In this way, decision-makers can be informed of potential offshore spillovers with ethical consequences in the energy transition scenarios¹². This underscores the need for more comprehensive models encompassing a wider array of environmental considerations and extending the assessment's geographical boundaries, ensuring a sustainable national energy transition.

Considering the complementary strengths of ESM and life cycle assessment (LCA), combining these two approaches offers multiple benefits¹³. LCA provides information on various environmental and resource-related performance indicators for a variety of economic activities and processes. Unlike ESM, LCA quantifies the environmental impacts of processes considering the value chain they contribute to, from raw material extraction to operation and end-of-life. This approach provides a granular view of potential environmental trade-offs and can be used to allocate impacts to end-consumers¹⁴. Applying LCA at the macroscale, including regions, nations, and markets, allows us to understand the broad implications and effectiveness of the energy transition¹⁵. Additionally, by incorporating geographic information into the life cycle inventory, LCA can identify the locations of impacts generated, thereby highlighting burden shifts across different regions¹⁶.

Despite growing interest in integrating ESM and LCA, a recent systematic review of over 900 studies concluded that no comprehensive

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applications of LCA to national carbon neutrality scenarios have been identified¹⁷. While some studies have made progress^{9,10,13}, key challenges remain. These include handling appropriate functional units that reflect the multifunctional nature of national scenarios, systematically avoiding double counting, and efficiently incorporating temporal considerations.

This study addresses these gaps by introducing an approach that integrates LCA with ESM to evaluate a long-term scenario that achieves net-zero territorial carbon dioxide emissions from Switzerland's fuel combustion and industrial processes and a counterpart baseline scenario. Comprehensive life cycle inventories are employed to capture environmental burdens across entire supply chains, from raw material extraction and energy conversion to the provision of useful energy services, encompassing both domestic and international processes.

The goal is to assess the life-cycle environmental impacts of Switzerland's energy transition by accounting for the entire supply chain of energy use. The functional unit is defined as the production, supply, and consumption of final energy in Switzerland from 2020 to 2050, including the necessary infrastructure for energy supply and use. This means that we not only consider the fuels and electricity consumed within Switzerland but also the upstream processes required to produce and deliver them. This approach ensures that environmental impacts across the entire supply chain are captured, including impacts that occur outside of Switzerland due to global supply chains.

To operationalize this integration, STEM results are used to adjust life cycle inventories for Swiss processes and supply chains. Simultaneously, outputs from integrated assessment models (IAMs) are used to adjust processes abroad, accounting for decarbonization efforts in the rest of the world through three background global scenarios from the REMIND model¹⁸ (<1.5 °C, <2 °C, and +3.5 °C). We then demonstrate the first application of the Python tool *pathways*¹⁹, which processes these modified inventories to calculate scenario-level life-cycle impacts, providing a transparent and reproducible framework for conducting LCA of ESM scenarios.

This case study illustrates the importance of decarbonization efforts beyond the national economy and evaluates environmental co-benefits and trade-offs associated with mitigating climate impacts. Through the workflow outlined, we calculate the life-cycle impacts of each flow of final energy consumed, reporting these impacts by life-cycle stage and geographical origin. This approach captures direct territorial emissions for net zero and upstream impacts in different world regions.

Results and discussion

Switzerland's journey to domestic net zero relies on renewable energy and carbon capture

We evaluate two scenarios to study Switzerland's energy transition: *Baseline* and *Net Zero*. *Baseline* represents continuing current trends in energy consumption and use. *Net Zero* outlines the necessary steps to achieve net-zero domestic carbon dioxide emissions by 2050, detailing the required configuration of the energy system to meet this target. These scenarios differ in key assumptions around technological advancements, geopolitical factors, and societal behaviors, which influence final energy consumption.

The key assumptions underlying these scenarios, including macro-economic projections, renewable energy potential, and transport demand, are summarized in Table 1, in the *Methods* section. A solution satisfying the objectives and constraints of both scenarios is provided by STEM, a comprehensive cost-optimization energy system model covering a wide array of energy technologies and sectors⁸. Figure 1 illustrates the system configurations resulting from each scenario, including the primary energy demand, disaggregated by primary energy carrier, and the direct carbon dioxide emissions associated with each economic sector.

The *Baseline* scenario underscores the consequences of maintaining current trends, highlighting the need for more ambitious policies to achieve stringent climate targets. Aligned closely with the "Weiter Wie Bisher" (WWB) scenario from the Energy Perspectives 2050+ report²⁰, the *Baseline* scenario shares similar assumptions regarding economic, demographic, and

technological trajectories. For example, both scenarios project comparable carbon dioxide emission levels by 2050. In the *Baseline* scenario, the energy system continues to rely on fossil fuels, with a reduced but persisting use of oil and natural gas. This persistence reflects the absence of additional climate policies and the continued use of fossil-based heating systems.

In contrast, the *Net Zero* scenario provides a pathway to domestic net-zero emissions, emphasizing substantial changes in energy sources. The energy mix shifts away from fossil fuels, with oil consumption declining to zero by 2050. Fossil gas usage also decreases from 117 PJ/year in 2020 to 33 PJ/year by 2050, while synthetic liquid fuels usage increases to 30 PJ/year by 2050, indicating a move towards low-carbon energy alternatives. Additionally, there is a notable reduction in primary energy consumption, primarily driven by electrification and the large-scale deployment of photovoltaics. Behavioral changes also play a role—for example, increased use of public transportation and decreased demand for private motorized transport (Table 1)—alongside improved energy efficiency measures across sectors and households.

An important aspect of the *Net Zero* scenario is the integration of carbon capture technologies and biogenic carbon flows, resulting in negative carbon dioxide emissions in specific sectors by 2050. For instance, power generation's emissions decrease from 2.6 Mt/year in 2020 to -0.4 Mt/year by 2050, and industry emissions fall from 6.5 Mt/year to 0.2 Mt/year in the same period, primarily due to the combined effects of moving away from combustion-based processes and implementing carbon capture and storage (CCS) on biomass (i.e., BECCS) and fossil-based power sources. Additionally, synthetic fuel net emissions reach -1.7 Mt/year in 2050, largely due to hydrogen production via gasification of woody biomass combined with CCS. This highlights the significance of different carbon dioxide reduction and removal technologies in this scenario to achieve the net-zero goal.

Emissions abroad are significant

Our modeling results show the life-cycle GHG emissions associated with the production, supply, and consumption of final energy in Switzerland for the *Baseline* and *Net Zero* scenarios. These emissions include the infrastructure to supply and use the energy. For example, a unit of energy used in a battery electric vehicle includes emissions related to the electricity grid construction, maintenance and losses as well as the charging infrastructure, electric motor and energy storage components of the vehicle.

Figure 2 demonstrates that while the Swiss energy system achieves net-zero GHG emissions by 2050, life-cycle emissions beyond its borders remain substantial. Evaluating the GHG flows, we observe that the main contributors to gross emissions within Switzerland are the heat and transport processes, which account for 11.3 Mt of emissions in 2050. These emissions are primarily offset by biogenic carbon flows into carbon sinks inside Switzerland and a fraction of the CCS and forestry activities occurring in Europe, as accounted for by the ESM.

This substantial balancing act shows progress within national borders. However, life-cycle emissions from processes abroad—mainly related to transport, manufacturing, and heat—result in 3.4 Mt of net emissions on the international level when considering the <2 °C global scenario. These 3.4 Mt constitute >10% of the net domestic GHG emissions in 2020 and 15% of the total net emissions projected in the *Baseline* scenario for 2050.

Figure 1 reports emissions as modeled in STEM, by final energy consumer, collapsing emissions from primary and secondary energy producers upstream (e.g., heat and electricity). Our approach, illustrated in Fig. 2, extends the analysis by disaggregating life-cycle emissions (or uptake) along the final energy supply chain by process. Hence, "Transport" on the emissions side (left side) represents the process of transport, with direct emissions related to fuel combustion, while emissions from manufacturing the fuel and related infrastructure are represented under the process of "Manufacture". This broader perspective captures emissions across the entire supply chain and allows us to categorize them by final energy consumer (as in Fig. 1), but also by life-cycle process (Fig. 2) and impacted geographies.

Breaking down the results by process over time, as shown in Fig. 3a, illustrates that while the heat and transport experience the most significant

Table 1 | Key assumptions of the two STEM scenarios, as described in Panos et al.³³ and Panos et al.⁵⁰

		'Baseline' scenario				'Net Zero' scenario			
		2020	2030	2040	2050	2020	2030	2040	2050
Macroeconomic	Population (million)	8.7	9.4	10.0	10.4	8.7	9.4	10.0	10.4
	Number of households (million)	3.9	4.2	4.5	4.7	3.9	4.2	4.5	4.7
	Working population (full-time equivalent)	4.3	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.3	4.5	4.6	4.7
	Reference GDP (billion CHF ₂₀₁₇)	695.6	846.4	981.6	1125.1	695.6	846.4	981.6	1125.1
Heating and cooling days	Heating degree days	3190	3105	2997	2928	3190	3105	3054	3030
	Cooling degree days	177	199	226	245	177	193	198	196
Fuel prices	Steam coal (USD ₂₀₂₂ /t)	56.0	67.0	67.8	69.0	56.0	57.0	50.0	43.0
	Natural gas (USD ₂₀₂₂ /MBtu)	4.7	6.9	6.9	7.1	4.7	4.5	4.3	4.1
	Crude oil (USD ₂₀₂₂ /barrel)	47.0	85.0	84.2	83.0	47.0	42.0	33.6	25.0
	Green hydrogen (USD ₂₀₂₂ /kg)	4.8	5.5	5.8	6.1	4.8	5.7	6.0	7.1
	Biodiesel (USD ₂₀₂₂ /GJ)	47.8	55.6	58.6	61.5	47.8	63.1	73.4	79.1
	Electricity (USD ₂₀₂₂ /MWh)	34.4	75.0	73.1	64.8	34.4	98.3	99.8	103.9
Renewable energy resources potential*	Hydropower excl. pump storage (TWh _e)	-	-	-	34-38.4 (36.4)	-	-	-	34-38.4 (36.4)
	Solar PV rooftop (TWh _e)	-	-	-	30-50 (40)	-	-	-	30-50 (40)
	Solar PV facades (TWh _e)	-	-	-	0-8 (4)	-	-	-	0-8 (4)
	Solar PV alpine (TWh _e)	-	-	-	0-30 (3)	-	-	-	0-30 (3)
	Wind turbines (TWh _e)	-	-	-	1.7-30 (4.3)	-	-	-	1.7-30 (4.3)
	Biomass wet and solid (TWh _t)	-	-	-	27.8-31.4 (29)	-	-	-	27.8-31.4 (29)
	Waste renewable and non-renewable** (TWh _t)	-	-	-	20.6 (20.6)	-	-	-	20.6 (20.6)
Geothermal electric (TWh _e)	-	-	-	0-4.3 (2.1)	-	-	-	0-4.3 (2.1)	
Passenger and freight transport demand	Motorized personal transport (Bpkm)	103.1	107.4	107.7	104.8	103.1	105.3	102.3	96.1
	Public road transport (Bpkm)	3.0	3.2	3.6	3.9	3.0	3.3	3.8	4.2
	Public rail transport (Bpkm)	23.9	25.6	28.5	30.7	23.9	26.1	29.9	33.3
	Freight road transport (Btkm)	17.1	18.0	19.6	21.2	17.1	17.4	18.4	19.3
	Freight rail transport (Btkm)	10.1	11.7	12.5	13.5	10.1	12.1	13.4	14.8

*Values are common across the two scenarios. Minimum–Maximum (Reference). ** This study assumes that 50% of waste incinerated consists of renewable materials (e.g., wood, paper, organic residues)⁵¹. This share remains constant over time.

reductions relative to 2020, they remain the main contributors to life-cycle GHG emissions. In 2020, net life-cycle emissions from heat generation and transport processes to satisfy the Swiss demand were 39 Mt, with 36 Mt emitted within Switzerland and 3 Mt abroad. By 2050, under the *Net Zero* scenario, total gross GHG emissions from heat generation and transport are projected to be 14 Mt, with 11 Mt emitted within Switzerland. Although the Swiss fraction is offset mainly by industrial carbon capture and biomass or electricity-based fuels, >3 Mt of CO₂-eq (net) are emitted from heat and transport activity processes outside Switzerland.

Figure 3b shows the breakdown of life-cycle GHG emissions by final energy consumer, highlighting the sectors driving these emissions. The case of the transport sector underscores the importance of considering global supply chain impacts when evaluating the environmental implications of policies. In 2020, passenger and goods transport emissions amounted to 22 Mt, with 15 Mt emitted within Switzerland. By 2050, the transport sector will see an uptake of synthetic fuels, battery electric, and fuel cell vehicles combined with the deployment of renewable sources of electricity, significantly reducing domestic GHG emissions. However, this sector's net life-cycle GHG emissions remain at 1.9 Mt that year, which explains >50% of the total net emissions.

Finally, Fig. 3c shows that in 2020, net emissions within Switzerland are 33 Mt, increasing to 45 Mt when accounting for supply chain emissions abroad. This indicates that almost 75% of the total emissions can currently be addressed through national policies. However, by 2050, while territorial GHG emissions are projected to be reduced to net zero, life-cycle emissions

outside of Switzerland remain substantial. Achieving net-zero emissions from a life-cycle perspective would require an additional yearly mitigation of 1.6, 3.4 and 4.7 Mt of GHG under the <1.5 °C, <2 °C, and +3.5 °C global scenarios, respectively. This analysis fundamentally shifts the decarbonization paradigm. While national efforts can significantly reduce emissions today, achieving further reductions as Switzerland reaches net-zero emissions requires understanding and addressing global supply chain emissions through a life-cycle perspective.

Reducing direct GHG emissions leads to trade-offs and co-benefits

Figure 4 presents the life cycle impact assessment of the *Net Zero* scenario in conjunction with the <2 °C global scenario. The analysis extends beyond global warming (Fig. 4a) to include other environmental indicators representing stressors on human health and ecosystems, showing both reduction and increase in impacts over time. The impacts are initially categorized by final energy consumers (left bars). Within each consumer category, impacts are further detailed by supply chain processes (middle bars). Lastly, the results are further specified by region of impact for each supply chain process (right bars).

Figure 4b illustrates the abiotic depletion of minerals and metals (i.e., not the physical volume demanded). This indicator, based on current production and reserves data, serves as a proxy for global elemental scarcity²¹. For example, this indicator weighs platinum scarcity 1600 times higher than copper's; copper's almost 26,000 times higher than iron's, and

Fig. 1 | Primary energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions scenarios for Switzerland. Primary energy consumption includes the total energy demand of all energy carriers, such as the energy used directly by end-users and conversion losses in

processes like thermal storage and electro-fuel synthesis. The ambient heat retrieved by heat pumps is counted as energy supply. The category “Other” includes the variables contributing <5% of the total. Detailed information can be found in the data repository³⁴.

Fig. 2 | Yearly life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions flow diagram of Switzerland in 2050. Life-cycle emissions based on Switzerland’s Net Zero energy scenario and the <2°C global scenario for 2050. Nodes represent various process categories contributing to GHG emissions and sinks. Red flows indicate emissions and uptake from processes within

Switzerland. Gray flows indicate emissions and uptake from processes outside of Switzerland, driven by Swiss demand for final energy. Green flows correspond to carbon sinks, including biogenic carbon uptake and carbon capture and storage (CCS). Finally, purple flows represent net emissions into the atmosphere.

antimony, the reference element, is weighted 700 times more scarce than copper. This indicator rises by more than two times between 2020 and 2050, illustrating the reliance of Switzerland’s ambitious energy transition on relatively-scarce metals.

The increased demand for mining and related mining waste treatment processes, which occur outside Switzerland, leads to significant

impacts in other environmental categories. Notably, the toxicity impact on freshwater ecosystems (Fig. 4c) is projected to double, predominantly caused by the leaching of metal-rich mine tailings into surrounding water bodies²². It is important to note, however, that we did not project a change in mining practices, which may partially mitigate the impacts quantified²³.

Fig. 3 | Yearly life-cycle greenhouse emissions associated with the supply and use of final energy in Switzerland. Life-cycle GHG emissions are quantified using IPCC's 2021 Global Warming Potential method⁵⁷, with a 100 year time horizon. Results are expressed in megatonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent (Mt CO₂-eq). The background life cycle inventory for Switzerland-based processes considers changes in the production system as modeled by STEM. The left bars represent the values for the *Baseline* scenario, and the right bars represent the *Net Zero* scenario values. These two scenarios are considered in combination with three global scenarios provided by the Integrated Assessment model REMIND (i.e., +3.5 °C, <2 °C and

<1.5 °C) to represent changes in the energy system outside of Switzerland, also considered in the life cycle inventory. The bars show the results for the <2 °C scenario by default. **a** The top plot shows life-cycle GHG emissions by supply chain process type. **b** The middle plot displays the life-cycle emissions by final energy consumer category. **c** The bottom plot displays these emissions by region: red bars for emissions within Switzerland, blue bars for Europe, and gray bars for the Rest of the World. A black horizontal line indicates the direct net emissions for Switzerland. Markers on the bottom plot indicate total life-cycle emissions across the three global scenarios.

Another key aspect is the formation of particulate matter (Fig. 4f). Decarbonizing the economy through the reduced use of combustion vehicles, furnaces, and boilers for industrial and heating purposes halves the domestic formation of particulate matter, decreasing from 10 kt to 5 kt of PM_{2.5}-eq. between 2020 and 2050. Although the increased use of biomass and agricultural waste in the *Net Zero* scenario adds to particulate matter emissions, this contribution does not offset the overall reductions. As a result, domestic emissions remain substantially lower in the *Net Zero* scenario compared to 2020 and slightly lower than in the *Baseline* scenario (5 kt vs 5.4 kt in 2050).

Considering the health benefits related to a decrease in exposure to particulate matter, a domestic reduction of 5 kt of these pollutants by the year 2050 can be monetarily valued at 235 M€₂₀₁₀/year, equivalent to ~30 €₂₀₁₀ per person annually. Furthermore, with respect to the *Baseline* scenario, the *Net Zero* scenario provides cumulative national savings estimated at ~2000 M€₂₀₁₀ between 2020 and 2050, or 178 €₂₀₁₀ per person. These valuations are calculated using the mean unit costs per kilogram of pollutant from Schmid et al.²⁴, informed by EcoSense²⁵ results.

Beyond domestic reductions, emissions abroad remain stable despite global decarbonization efforts. To illustrate this geographic shift, we focus on the passenger car sector. Figure 5 provides a flow diagram of particulate matter formation related to the main hotspot, passenger cars operation in Switzerland, comparing the years 2020 and 2050. In 2020, total life-cycle particulate matter formation amounted to 10.3 kt PM_{2.5}-eq, arising from the 140 PJ energy consumption by passenger cars. By 2050, final energy use is more than halved to 57 PJ due to efficient electric drivetrains, and domestic emissions are nearly eliminated. However, global life-cycle emissions only decrease to 6.7 kt PM_{2.5}-eq. These emissions persist abroad because of the mining requirements to supply copper, graphite, iridium, and platinum for producing battery cells and fuel cell stacks. This occurs despite technological advancements such as doubling the energy density of battery cells between 2020 and 2050 (i.e., the battery mass halves for a same range autonomy), and reduced use of iridium and platinum in electrolyzers and fuel cell stacks.

Overall, while the total formation of particulate matter is reduced, the shift in emissions sources highlights the complexity of global supply chains. In 2020, mining activity processes are responsible for 30% of 32 kt of particulate matter emissions, increasing to 50% of 28 kt by 2050. This underscores the spatial environmental trade-offs involved in the transition to a net-zero GHG economy. Yet, given the often-isolated location of mining sites, the extent to which local populations are affected by this increase in particulate matter emissions remains difficult to quantify without a detailed regionalized impact assessment.

While global impacts are significant, domestic environmental changes are equally important. Land use (Fig. 4d), measured in km²-year, reflects the total surface area occupied over time. This indicator shows an increase of over 70% between 2020 and 2050, with most land used in Switzerland. These land use impacts are based on the life cycle database, *ecoinvent*, which provides land occupation and transformation factors for each activity. Forestry activities, linked to biodiversity impacts²⁶, play a significant role in this category, supporting electricity production, combined heat and power (CHP) units for district heating, and providing wood-based hydrogen and ethanol for vehicles. This does not entail the expansion of forestry into new land areas. Instead, it reflects the utilization of untapped biomass potential from existing Swiss forests. To align resource use with projected availability,

the ESM applies a constraint on biomass utilization based on its energy potential, informed by detailed assessments³⁷, rather than land availability (Table 1).

Finally, while freshwater use (Fig. 4e) increases by 25% from 2020 to 2050, domestic freshwater use decreases by 10% during the same period. As a result, the share of freshwater use occurring within Switzerland drops from 83% of the total impact in 2020 to 60% in 2050. Electricity generation is the major contributor in this category; hydroelectric reservoirs play a significant role in Switzerland's energy mix, resulting in considerable water evaporation. In relative terms, the water demand for electrolysis remains modest, and biomass-based fuels carry a limited water footprint (as the feedstock is from biomass residuals).

Life-cycle insights into energy transitions

This study applies a life-cycle perspective to evaluate a long-term scenario that achieves net-zero territorial carbon dioxide emissions from Switzerland's energy supply and industrial processes. While the scenario achieves the domestic net-zero goal and significant reductions of overall GHG emissions, a life-cycle perspective points to additional mitigation requirements. Thus, overlooking life-cycle emissions can undermine the net decarbonization results driven by national energy system models.

Furthermore, GHG emissions reduction can lead to an increase and/or spatial shift in other environmental burdens. For instance, transitioning to electric mobility will reduce local air pollution, but it partially displaces burdens like particulate matter formation from urban to mining areas and increases toxicity impacts in these regions. This shift highlights the complexity of global supply chains and the necessity for a life-cycle perspective that accounts for environmental impacts beyond global warming when planning national energy system transitions. It also shows the necessity of implementing climate and broader environmental policies on a global scale to ensure their effectiveness and support a just transition worldwide. Additionally, it underscores the importance of regionalized impact assessments to fully understand the effects of changes in the energy system on human health and ecosystem damages¹⁵.

Our results indicate an increased demand for scarce metals, posing significant challenges to resource availability and the feasibility of energy transition scenarios. This increased demand –even when considering advancements in circularity– has profound implications for raw material extraction and the global competition for their access²⁸. Recent reports from institutions such as the European Commission²⁹ and the U.S. Department of Energy³⁰ have emphasized the strategic imperative of securing a reliable and adequate supply of critical raw materials. Hence, while ESMs (and IAMs) provide a high-level perspective on potential energy futures, they would benefit from greater technological and material resolution to capture the environmental and material implications of deploying a given technology over another.

Advancing the integration of LCA and ESM

Efforts to integrate a life-cycle perspective into ESMs are essential to comprehensively address all environmental impacts, allocating impacts to consumers. This study demonstrates a first step in this direction, developing the tools and workflow to systematically and effectively evaluate the life-cycle impacts of ESM scenarios. The next step involves incorporating these life-cycle considerations into the cost-optimized engine of the ESM.

Several methods have been proposed in the literature to combine LCA with ESMS. However, widely accepted and reproducible integration tools are still lacking. Existing alternatives include single-objective optimization, where environmental impacts are monetized and different weighting factors for costs are defined across environmental categories to find the least-cost scenario¹⁰; and multi-objective optimization, as applied in Vandepaer et al.¹⁰.

A third strategy involves introducing caps on LCA indicators, setting absolute cumulative limits on certain environmental impacts⁹.

These approaches expand the scope of assessment metrics beyond energy, costs, and carbon dioxide emissions to include indicators such as biodiversity, human health impacts, and resource depletion. These broader metrics would allow for benchmarking scenarios against planetary

Fig. 4 | Yearly life cycle impact assessment of Switzerland’s Net Zero scenario with a consumer, supply chain, and geographic perspective. The life cycle impact assessment is based on Switzerland’s Net Zero scenario and the <2 °C global scenario. The left-most bars in each of the panels for each year represent impacts across final energy consumers. The middle bars represent impacts across supply chain processes for a given final energy consumer. The right-most bars represent the origins of impacts across regions for a given supply chain process. Narrow white stripes visible between bar segments are used to separate contributions by region, process, and consumer. In cases where contributions are very small, these separating lines may obscure those contributors. **a** Climate change: GHG warming impact over a 100 year time horizon. Results are expressed in megatonnes of CO₂-eq. **b** Metals/

minerals depletion: demand for minerals and metals extraction relative to antimony scarcity. Current recycling rates used (the changes in recycling rates are not projected into the future). Results are expressed in kilotonnes of Sb (antimony)-eq. **c** Freshwater ecotoxicity: emissions of chemicals harmful to freshwater ecosystems. Results are expressed in megatonnes of dichlorobenzene-eq⁵⁸. **d** Land use: land area (of all types) occupied over time. Results are expressed in square kilometres-year. **e** Freshwater use: difference between freshwater abstraction and release (i.e., evaporation and water contained in products). Results are expressed in cubic kilometres of freshwater and do not consider the scarcity at the abstraction site⁵⁸. **f** Particulate matter formation: formation of particle-like air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO_x). Results are expressed in kilotonnes of PM_{2.5}-eq⁵⁸.

Fig. 5 | Flow diagram of yearly life-cycle particulate matter emissions from Swiss passenger cars. The flow diagram assesses the life-cycle emissions of passenger cars operated in Switzerland for 2020 (left plot) and 2050 (right plot). These results are based on Switzerland’s Net Zero and the <2 °C global scenarios. Nodes represent various supply chain processes contributing to particulate matter formation. Red flows linking to “Direct emissions” indicate emissions within Switzerland, while gray

flows linking to processes represent emissions beyond Switzerland. Domestic emissions in 2050 are nearly eliminated (see “Direct emissions”). These emissions do not include uncertain abrasion emissions from brake, tire, and road wear, which are left outside the final energy system boundaries (see Methods section). Flows representing <1% of total emissions are not shown.

boundaries, offering a more systematic and comprehensive understanding of the potential co-benefits and trade-offs between decarbonization and other environmental goals.

Strengths, limitations, and future directions

Benchmarking the approach proposed in this study against alternative methods like multi-regional input-output (MRIO) models highlights complementary strengths. MRIO models, widely used to evaluate national emissions from a consumer perspective, provide a broad view of global trade flows³¹. They excel at capturing trade-related emissions and environmental impacts across global supply chains, enabling a comprehensive economy-wide perspective³². However, they lack the technological granularity within each sector provided by process-based LCA. In contrast, our approach enables more detailed evaluations by identifying the specific technologies contributing to impacts across environmental indicators and material demand. Moreover, it incorporates structural changes by integrating updated parameters from ESMs and IAMs—such as process efficiencies, learning curves, and technological advancements.

While the proposed approach provides valuable insights, it is limited by the granularity mismatch between STEM, REMIND, and life cycle inventory datasets. ESMs and IAMs often lack specificity on technologies, such as PV types or battery chemistries, requiring assumptions during mapping, which introduces uncertainties (see *Methods* for a detailed explanation of our approach). Additionally, the *premise* framework does not fully decarbonize all sectors in global scenarios, potentially leading to over- or underestimation of impacts. Addressing these limitations will require more harmonized datasets, improved mapping processes, and iterative feedback

loops between LCA and ESM/IAM stages to enhance accuracy and consistency.

Methods

STEM modeling framework

The ESM framework, upon which this work is built, consists of a large set of mathematical models orchestrated to provide a comprehensive view of the transformation of the Swiss economy and energy system towards achieving net-zero carbon dioxide emissions by 2050. Detailed descriptions of the STEM model and the evaluated pathways can be found in Panos et al.⁶ and Panos et al.³³, respectively. The pathways evaluated in this study correspond to the SURE Pathway Scenarios (SPS) 1 and 4. “*SPS1: Team Sprint. Focus on Sustainability*” aligns with the *Net Zero* scenario, while “*SPS4: Walk & Talk. Current Trends and Policies*” serves as the *Baseline* scenario. STEM includes only carbon dioxide from energy and industrial processes, as well as those directly linked to energy provision (e.g., emissions from biomass used for energy, but not from agriculture related to food production). Regarding the transport sector, it follows the territorial approach. Thus, carbon dioxide emissions are accounted to the country of purchase. The detailed results used for this study can be found in the data repository³⁴.

The coupling of ESM and LCA

Integrating insights from ESM and IAM into LCA to extend present-day life cycle inventories into the future has become a structured approach, establishing the methodological foundation for prospective LCA. This integration, initiated by Mendoza Beltran et al.³⁵ and formalized by the Python library *premise*³⁶, enables LCA to incorporate process and technology-specific forecasts from ESMs and IAMs. These include learning curves,

Fig. 6 | Projected chemistry-specific battery market shares. Adapted from Degen et al.⁴². NCA Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide. NMC Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide. NMC900-Si Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide with Silicon Anode. LFP

Lithium Iron Phosphate. SIB Sodium-Ion Battery. ASSB All-Solid-State Battery. LSB Lithium-Sulfur Battery. LAB Lithium-Air Battery.

technological developments, emerging technologies, and other evolving energy system parameters such as electricity mixes. In this study, a prospective LCA approach is used to quantify the environmental burdens of global supply chains in line with ESM and IAM scenarios. Life cycle inventories are projected into the future using *premise*³⁶.

For processes occurring within Switzerland, projections are based on results from STEM. To ensure consistency across the STEM scenarios and the LCA database, each variable representing energy conversion, transmission, distribution, and consumption within the STEM framework is harmonized and linked to the corresponding life cycle inventory. This process ensures that technological parameters, process efficiencies, and energy markets modeled in STEM are accurately reflected in the life cycle inventories used for impact assessment.

For processes in other world regions, projections are informed by the REMIND integrated assessment model¹⁸. Three REMIND scenarios are considered in this study: SSP2-NPi, SSP2-PkBudg1150, and SSP2-PkBudg500. The first scenario reflects the current trajectory based on existing national policies (NPi), under which global mean temperature could rise over 3.5 degrees Celsius by the end of the century. The second scenario limits global warming to ~2 degrees Celsius, with a global carbon budget of 1150 Gt of CO₂ for the entire century. The third scenario is intended to limit global warming to 1.5 degrees Celsius, with a global carbon budget of 500 Gt of CO₂. These scenarios capture different levels of ambition and risk associated with transitioning to a low-carbon future, providing a comprehensive range of potential pathways and their impacts³⁷.

To calculate the life-cycle environmental impacts of the scenarios, we use the Python package *pathways*¹⁹. This open-source tool builds on *brightway*³⁸ and is model-agnostic, allowing reproducibility across different datasets and ESMs. *pathways* processes a data package that includes scenario data from the ESM and mapping details to retrieve the corresponding

LCA dataset for each technology present in the ESM. For this study, inputs include:

1. Scenario-modified technosphere and biosphere LCA matrices generated by *premise*;
2. Production volumes for each time step from STEM scenarios;
3. Metadata files linking scenario variables to LCA datasets.

pathways carries out calculations using *bw2calc*, the calculation module of *brightway*. Finally, some post-processing to address potential double-counting issues is performed. The tool returns the environmental impacts broken down by environmental indicator, product or service consumer, geographical location of consumer, time step, geographical origin of impacts, and life-cycle stage.

Despite the growing body of literature using LCA to evaluate ESM-based scenarios^{9,10,13,39–41}, these efforts remain fragmented, with inconsistent methodologies and varying scopes. Much like the early stages of prospective LCA, there is a clear need to consolidate workflows, streamline methodologies, and develop tools that ensure reproducibility, computational efficiency, and methodological transparency. This study addresses these challenges by demonstrating a streamlined, model-agnostic methodology that integrates *premise* and *pathways*. By proposing a reproducible workflow applicable to various ESMs, IAMs and LCA databases, we aim to establish a standardized framework for future LCA applications in energy system modeling.

Mapping between STEM variables and life cycle assessment

The mapping between final energy consumers in STEM and LCA datasets is described in the scenario data package's mapping file config.yaml found under the folder configuration_file in the online repository. The LCA datasets used for each final energy consumer of the STEM scenario are

Table 2 | Current and projected battery energy density values

Type	Current			2050		
	Specific energy density [kWh/kg cell]	Battery energy density [kWh/kg battery]	Source	Specific energy density [kWh/kg cell]	Battery energy density [kWh/kg battery]	Source
Li-ion, NMC111	0.18	0.13	Hasselwander et al. ⁵²	0.2	0.15	Maximum interval value for current energy density used as future mean
Li-ion, NMC523	0.2	0.15		0.22	0.16	
Li-ion, NMC622	0.24	0.18		0.26	0.19	
Li-ion, NMC811	0.28	0.2		0.34	0.24	
Li-ion, NMC955	0.34	0.24		0.38	0.27	
Li-ion, NCA	0.28	0.2		0.34	0.24	
Li-ion, LFP	0.16	0.13		0.22	0.18	
Li-ion, LiMn2O4	0.11	0.09	Ecoinvent 3.10 ⁵³	0.11	0.08	No improvement considered
Li-ion, LTO	0.05	0.03	Wang et al. ⁵⁴	0.05	0.03	No improvement considered
Li-sulfur, Li-S	0.15	0.11	Wickerts et al. ⁵⁵	0.34	0.26	Duffner et al. ⁵⁶
Li-oxygen, Li-O2	0.36	0.2	Duffner et al. ⁵⁶	0.93	0.51	Duffner et al. ⁵⁶

Fig. 7 | Yearly life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions flow diagram of Switzerland in 2050, Baseline scenario. Life-cycle emissions based on Switzerland’s Baseline energy scenario and the <2 °C global scenario for 2050. Nodes represent various process categories contributing to GHG emissions and sinks. Red flows indicate emissions and uptake from processes within Switzerland. Gray flows indicate

emissions and uptake from processes outside of Switzerland, driven by Swiss demand for final energy. Green flows correspond to carbon sinks, including biogenic carbon uptake and carbon capture and storage (CCS). Finally, purple flows represent net emissions into the atmosphere.

available in the file lci-sweet_sure.xlsx under the folder inventories in the online repository³⁴.

Functional units and life cycle inventory

As described above, each STEM variable representing a final energy consumer is matched with an LCA dataset. For example, the LCA datasets that represent the consumption of final energy in vehicles include the supply of energy to the vehicle (e.g., gasoline, diesel, electricity, hydrogen) but also the storage component needed to store the energy on the road (e.g., fuel tank, hydrogen tank, battery) and the components needed to turn it into kinetic energy (e.g., internal combustion engine, electric motor). Using the kilometer lifetime of the vehicle and its tank-to-wheel energy consumption, we

derive the fraction of the energy storage component needed per megajoule of energy consumed. The other vehicle components (e.g., glider, suspension, etc.) are left outside the energy system’s scope.

For vehicles equipped with a battery (i.e., passenger cars, buses, trucks, two-wheelers, etc.), the “Mixed” scenario from Degen et al.⁴² is used. As shown in Fig. 6, it foresees the continued market deployment of lithium-ion batteries (i.e., Li-NMC and Li-LFP) until 2030 with a tendency toward nickel-rich and cobalt-poor chemistries (i.e., Li-NMC 955) and silicon-coated anodes (e.g., Li-NMC900-Si). After 2030, the scenario introduces post-lithium chemistries (e.g., solid-state, sodium-ion), which reach a 39% market share by 2040. We add the market shares of solid-state batteries to that of sodium-ion batteries due to a lack of inventory data. For 2050, market

shares for 2040 are used. Concurrently, the energy density of the cells also improves over time, as shown in Table 2.

Other datasets representing the consumption of final energy by a specific consumer include the infrastructure needed to consume the energy (e.g., boiler, furnace, heat pump) and the supply of 1 MJ of energy entering the conversion system. In all instances of combustion, the LCA dataset

includes the combustion products. For example, modeling the consumption of 1 MJ of wood pellets in an 80% efficient wood pellet stove is achieved by requiring the supply of 0.8 MJ of heat from a wood pellet-fired stove.

As described above, the LCA datasets used for each final energy consumer of the STEM scenario are available in the file lci-sweet_sure.xlsx under the folder inventories in the online repository.

Fig. 8 | Yearly life cycle impact assessment of Switzerland's Baseline scenario with a consumer, supply chain, and geographic perspective. The life cycle impact assessment is based on Switzerland's Baseline scenario and the <2 °C global scenario. The left-most bars in each of the panels for each year represent impacts across final energy consumers. The middle bars represent impacts across supply chain activities for a given final energy consumer. The right-most bars represent the origins of impacts across regions for a given supply chain process. Narrow white stripes visible between bar segments are used to separate contributions by region, process, and consumer. In cases where contributions are very small, these separating lines may obscure those contributors. **a** Climate change: GHG warming impact over a 100-year time horizon. Results are expressed in megatonnes of CO₂-eq. **b** Metals/minerals

depletion: demand for minerals and metals extraction relative to antimony scarcity. Current recycling rates used (the changes in recycling rates are not projected into the future). Results are expressed in kilotonnes of Sb (antimony)-eq. **c** Freshwater ecotoxicity: emissions of chemicals harmful to freshwater ecosystems. Results are expressed in megatonnes of dichlorobenzene-eq⁵⁸. **d** Land use: land area (of all types) occupied over time. Results are expressed in square kilometers-year. **e** Freshwater use: difference between freshwater abstraction and release (i.e., evaporation and water contained in products). Results are expressed in cubic kilometers of freshwater and do not consider the scarcity at the abstraction site⁵⁸. **f** Particulate matter formation: formation of particle-like air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO_x). Results are expressed in kilotonnes of PM_{2.5}-eq⁵⁸.

The ecoinvent LCA database v.3.10 (system model “allocation, cut-off by classification”) serves as the primary source for background inventory data, further modified by *premise* to align with a combination of global and Swiss scenarios. Complementing this, the *premise* library enriches the database by including inventories for emerging technologies and mining activities. Current LCI databases often exhibit gaps, particularly in representing critical raw materials, such as rhenium, rare earth oxides, and platinum group metals. Though used in small quantities, these materials play a pivotal role in various technologies and are frequently underrepresented or completely absent in existing inventories. Building on the work by Schlichenmaier and Naegler (2022)⁴³, additional data is collected for electric and internal combustion engine vehicles, wind turbines, photovoltaic panels, concentrated solar power projects, nuclear plants, electric batteries, fuel cells, and electrolyzers.

Since metals are primarily traded globally, we model world markets for the various metals assessed. In these markets, the contribution of different mining and refining regions corresponds to their current market shares. Following this approach, the supply from different regions for a specific metal will be directly proportional to the country-level contributions to the global market. We derive these shares from various sources, mainly the British Geological Survey (BGS)⁴⁴ and the United States Geological Survey (USGS)⁴⁵, in addition to data from van den Brink et al.⁴⁶ for antimony refining. For certain metals where data is accessible (e.g., lithium, cobalt), we incorporate projections from BloombergNEF regarding the development of future mining and refining projects to forecast the market shares' evolution up to 2030⁴⁷. The metal markets also account for the average transport distances and modalities of the metal product from producer to consumer. This data is retrieved from The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD)⁴⁸.

These data and its implementation can be found in the *premise* online code repository⁴⁹. The data pertaining to the implementation of the STEM SPS scenarios into LCA, including the mapping between STEM technology variables and LCA datasets, are contained in the scenario online repository³⁴.

Endogeneity and double-counting

In the context of combining LCA with ESM, double-counting needs addressing as ESM typically generate aggregate demand scenarios without distinguishing between intermediate and final energy demand. When these aggregate demands are used as inputs for LCA, there is a risk of counting the same resource use more than once. This is particularly problematic when assessing the environmental impacts of interconnected systems where the outputs of one process serve as inputs for another. If the demand for these materials is not carefully allocated between processes, the total environmental impact can be overestimated, resulting in misleading conclusions about the performance of the scenarios under analysis. Hence, the focus is on evaluating the total quantities yielded by the ESM's final output rather than the quantities provided by examining the supply chain as provided by LCA. To achieve this, the original life cycle inventory database is modified by zeroing out all regional energy inputs that are considered and potentially required by the energy system model throughout its life cycle, adhering to the rationale presented in Volkart et al.⁹. In this case, we focus on the inventories mapped as final energy providers. This approach is

implemented in a systematic and reproducible manner, effectively isolating the quantities of interest and preventing the inflation of resource use that would otherwise occur due to supply chain overlaps. Consequently, this method enhances the accuracy of the life cycle impact assessment.

However, the issue of double-counting is not completely eliminated and requires a more complex algorithm to be fully addressed throughout the LCA database. Indeed, double-counting persists because of how energy service demands in ESM, particularly global ones, are evaluated. Double-counting occurs when calculating energy service demands in ESM (e.g., tonnes of steel and chemicals) because mining and construction activities are also represented and included in an aggregated form. These calculations do not consider adjustments from a LCA perspective. Specifically, the tonnes of steel assumed in ESMs when calculating the energy used for production may not align with and have not been adjusted to reflect LCA calculations.

Baseline scenario results

While the main results focus on the *Net Zero* scenario, analogous results for the *Baseline* scenario are presented in Figs. 7 and 8, providing additional context on Switzerland's life-cycle impacts.

Data availability

The results presented in this study can be found in the following code repository: https://github.com/premise-community-scenarios/sweet_sure-2050-switzerland.

Code availability

The code required to reproduce the results presented in this study can be found in the following code repository: https://github.com/premise-community-scenarios/sweet_sure-2050-switzerland. The workflow requires *premise* and *pathways*, both open-sourced and installable via the Python package repository Pypi. However, the workflow also requires a valid license to the ecoinvent LCA database, which should be obtained from the Ecoinvent Association (<https://ecoinvent.org/>).

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Author contributions

Conceptualization and methodology, A.J.H.M. and R.S.; formal analysis, A.J.H.M., E.P., R.S.; software, R.S., and A.J.H.M.; validation, A.J.H.M., and R.S.; writing – original draft, A.J.H.M.; writing – review and editing, C.B., C.M., E.P., P.B, R.M., and R.S.; funding acquisition, C.B. and P.B.

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